

OPPORTUNITIES FOR A RESEARCH AGENDA ON CLIMATE AND DISASTER RISK FINANCE AND INSURANCE IN UZBEKISTAN

OPPORTUNITIES FOR A RESEARCH AGENDA ON CLIMATE AND DISASTER RISK FINANCE AND INSURANCE (CDRFI) IN UZBEKISTAN

Author:

Cristian Camilo Fernández Lopera

PhD C. Risk Observatory –OSIRIS, Centre for Social Studies (CES); Faculty of Economics, University of Coimbra.

Visiting Scientist: CARSJ project (No. 101086415) – Caucasus and Central Asia Research Social Innovation: Development Assistance, Innovation, and Societal Transformation, funded by the Horizon Marie Curie Staff Exchange programme. Faculty of Economics, University of Coimbra.

The findings, interpretations, and conclusions expressed in this work do not necessarily reflect the views of the Risk Observatory – OSIRIS, the Centre for Social Studies (CES), the Faculty of Economics of the University of Coimbra, or the CARSJ project and its members.

Tashkent,
August 2024.

Table of Contents

<i>Abbreviations and acronyms</i>	1
1. Introduction	1
2. Methodology	3
2.1 <i>Review of gray and academic literature</i>	3
2.2 <i>Analysis-Synthesis Matrix</i>	3
3. Disaster risk conditions in Uzbekistan	4
3.1. <i>Climate-related hazards</i>	4
3.2. <i>Socioeconomic vulnerability to disasters</i>	5
3.3. <i>Major recent climate-related disaster events.</i>	6
3.4. <i>Disaster risk conditions</i>	6
3.5. <i>Disaster risk management capacities</i>	9
3.5.1. <i>Institutions and legal framework for DRM and CDRFI</i>	9
3.5.2. <i>Disaster risk knowledge</i>	10
3.5.3. <i>Financial protection and climate risk insurance</i>	11
4. CDRFI-related programs and projects in Uzbekistan	14
5. Relevant stakeholders related to Climate and Disaster Risk Finance and Insurance (CDRFI) in Uzbekistan	15
6. Most relevant sectors for implementing CDRFI mechanisms in Uzbekistan	17
6.1 <i>Public sector</i>	17
6.2 <i>Private sector</i>	17
7. Identification of topics for a potential CDRFI research agenda	18
8. Time table for the implementation of the research agenda	21
9. Conclusions	22
<i>Acknowledgements</i>	23
10. References	23

List of Figures

Figure 1. Number of people affected by natural hazards during 1980 and 2020.	5
Figure 2. Flood prone regions in Uzbekistan.	7
Figure 3. Average annual loss by floods.	8
Figure 4. Flood in Sardoba, Uzbekistan, June 2020	9
Figure 5. Inputs and outputs for the definition of topics for a CDRFI research agenda in Uzbekistan.	18

Abbreviations and acronyms

CC	Climate Change
CDRFI	Climate and Disaster Risk Finance and Insurance
CRI	Climate Risk Insurance
DRM	Disaster Risk Management
GoU	Government of Uzbekistan
IMDA	Insurance Market Development Agency
MAWR	Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources
MES	Ministry of Emergency Situations
MoF	Ministry of Finance
SSP	Shared Socioeconomic Pathways

1. Introduction

Climate-related disasters are the most significant worldwide in terms of recurrence and impact. According to CRED (2023), in 2022, out of 387 major disasters, 335 were climate-related, with floods and storms being the most frequent. In 2022, extreme temperatures caused 16,416 deaths, floods caused 7,954 deaths, and droughts caused 2,601 deaths. Regarding economic losses, storms, floods, and droughts are the costliest events (Ibid). This situation requires attention on how different stakeholders project their development and how they reduce their disaster risks.

Alimonti and Mariani's (2023) research suggests that the number of deaths caused by disasters has been decreasing over the past 80 years, with projections indicating a reduction of around 200 fewer disasters by 2030 and less than half by 2050 (Alimonti and Mariani, 2023, p. 13). However, the number of people affected, economic costs, and migration have been increasing over the past three decades, deteriorating the quality of life for the population, particularly for the most marginalized groups. It is worth noting that the increase in disaster impacts is not due to an increase in the occurrence of catastrophic hazards but rather due to an increase in exposed elements and improved frequency and quality of reports from national and international organizations. Climate-related risks and disasters are particularly representative in Uzbekistan. Such events have caused an average annual fatality rate of 219 and direct economic losses of around \$2.8 billion, which is approximately 2.8% of the country's nominal GDP (CAREC, 2022).

Aiming to reduce the impacts of climate-related events, governments have implemented various strategies that include the process of risk knowledge, risk reduction, and disaster management. One of the most widely used disaster risk reduction tools is Climate and Disaster Risk Finance and Insurance (CDRFI), which aims to reduce the socioeconomic impacts of climate-related events on the most vulnerable population groups.

CDRFI focuses on the financial component of disaster risk management (DRM) and, among other components, includes financial protection. Financial protection is defined as the set of financial mechanisms or instruments for risk retention and risk transfer established in advance to access economic resources after the occurrence of emergencies, seeking timely attention and recovery (DRFIP, 2023; Marulanda et al., 2014). The financial protection mechanisms are implemented based on the disaster risk conditions in the area of interest. Thus, the risk characteristics in terms of impact and recurrence indicate the most appropriate type of CDRFI mechanism. Among other CDRFI mechanisms, the following stand out: mitigation funds, loans, and direct payments; insurance and reinsurance; catastrophe bonds; climate derivatives; contingent credits; reconstruction loans; catastrophic insurance; and funds and loans for prevention (Fernández Lopera, 2020).

DRFI has been recognized by the Hyogo Framework for Action (2005-2015) (UNDRR, 2005) and by the Sendai Framework for Action (2015-2030) (UNGA, 2015) as a viable strategy for mitigating the effects of climate change (CC), particularly in the face of hydrometeorological phenomena such as droughts, floods, and tropical cyclones. This has been promoted by international development policies and has been established as one of the five pillars of a comprehensive DRM approach.

However, efforts to develop CDRFI in middle and low-income countries remain insufficient in meeting the needs of the most vulnerable populations (Tang et al., 2021). Various authors (Delavallade et al., 2015) have highlighted the persisting protection gap against climate risk between high-income countries and middle and low-income countries, despite international efforts to promote CDRFI mechanisms such as climate risk insurance (CRI). This gap exacerbates the unequal distribution of economic resources, perpetuating conditions of inequality and disaster vulnerability. Consequently, there is a need for the definition of research topics that lead to concrete implementations of socially inclusive CDRFI. This will enable national and local stakeholders to reduce their vulnerability to disasters.

According to Takeuchi, Skalon, and Gurenko (2018, p. 10), the Government of Uzbekistan (GoU) recognizes the crucial role of CDRFI and CRI – insuring the population living in risky areas is achieved through several decrees and a law; CRI is also a priority for insurance market development. The GoU acknowledges that improving the environment for CRI market development and gaining a better understanding of its operational details is a priority for the country in reducing its fiscal vulnerability.

Considering the challenges that arise from the implementation of CDRFI mechanisms, this document aims to provide an overview of CDRFI in Uzbekistan, serving as input for the identification of a CDRFI research agenda. The findings of this study will inform national and international research institutes and national DRM authorities. The outcomes of this document are summarized in a timeline composed of 14 activities that will enable the development of the research agenda in the future.

The implementation of the research agenda is expected to be guided by the Insurance Department of Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE), Uzbekistan, with the support of the Risk Observatory of the Centre for Social Studies and the Faculty of Economics at the University of Coimbra, Portugal.

2. Methodology

To achieve the objective, this study uses secondary data to provide an overview of disaster risk conditions in Uzbekistan, highlighting the most representative hazards, socioeconomic vulnerability to disasters, and exposure of vulnerable groups to climate-related hazards. This provides a contextualization for the subsequent activities. The methodology focuses on reviewing information sources that serve as a basis for identifying gaps in components such as information, data, public policies, the public and private sector.

Subsequently, the identification of past and current programs and projects related to CDRFI in the country provides a list of topics already addressed and an approximation to the knowledge gaps regarding CDRFI. This identification leads this research to identifying relevant stakeholders related to CDRFI in Uzbekistan. Next, aiming to zoom in on specific needs, this study identifies the most suitable regions and economic sectors for implementing CDRFI. Consequently, the overview of disaster risk conditions and general CDRFI state will provide a foundation for identifying crucial topics that should be included in a research agenda. Finally, this study condenses its results in a timeline for the implementation of the research agenda, outlining its respective activities and timeframes.

2.1 Review of gray and academic literature

To establish the state of the art of sociodemographic variables and indicators, this study relies on Google Scholar, an open and free search engine, using predefined search criteria. These criteria are as follows:

- **Search engine:** Google for institutional publications or grey literature and Google Scholar, focusing on indexed journals and full references (no citations).
- **Keywords:** Adaptation to climate change in Uzbekistan; Natural hazards in Uzbekistan; Disaster risks in Uzbekistan; Climate insurance in Uzbekistan; Risk transfer, financial protection; Gender vulnerability in Uzbekistan; Socioeconomic vulnerability in Uzbekistan.
- **Temporal scope:** The period from 2005 to 2024 was selected, which corresponds to the implementation of international public policy frameworks such as the Hyogo Framework for Action and the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). This search period aims to capture a timeframe characterized by a shift in focus towards disaster risk reduction and CDRFI at the international level.
- **Language:** English.

2.2 Analysis-Synthesis Matrix

For the analysis of the literature, a matrix is designed to link the eight key words mentioned above. Subsequently, the most representative documents and sources of information are identified as inputs for the development of the chapter on relevant actors and sectors.

Of the 38 reviewed articles, 17 documents were incorporated into the analysis. Their inclusion depended on the relevance of the study and its relation to CDRFI. Natural hazards were the most frequently published topics, while publications on risk transfer, climate risk insurance, and socioeconomic vulnerability to disasters were the least common.

Table 1. Results of the literature review as inputs for the development of the study.

Key words	Results	Reviewed	Included
Adaptation to climate change in Uzbekistan	20	5	2
Natural hazards in Uzbekistan	15	4	4
Financial protection in Uzbekistan	5	3	3
Disaster risk management in Uzbekistan	43	5	1
Disaster risks in Uzbekistan	12	4	2
Climate insurance in Uzbekistan	32	6	1
Risk transfer in Uzbekistan	3	3	1
Gender vulnerability in Uzbekistan	18	5	2
Socioeconomic vulnerability in Uzbekistan.	67	3	1

3. Disaster risk conditions in Uzbekistan

This section provides an overview of the main hazards, socioeconomic vulnerability conditions to disasters, and the country's capacities to prevent, respond, and recover from climate-related events. Thus, this section aims to elaborate on the general features of disaster risk conditions and the main actions of disaster risk management (DRM) in Uzbekistan.

3.1. Climate-related hazards

According to the World Bank (2021), climate-related hazards are the most prevalent in Uzbekistan. These hazards affect the agricultural sector primarily through seasonal flooding and droughts. The World Bank stated that "Impacts from CC make Uzbekistan increasingly vulnerable to droughts, high temperatures, heat waves, heavy precipitation, mudflows, floods, and avalanches" (World Bank, 2021, p. 1). In terms of recurrence and impacts in a future climate, droughts pose a significant concern, as this type of hazard may become more frequent due to decreases in river runoff, specifically from the Amu Darya and Syr Darya Rivers. Aridity and drought risks are high during vegetation periods, especially in areas with growing economic and population demands.

In Uzbekistan, major climate-related risks include water scarcity, heat waves, and extremely hot days (over 39°C). Eight out of 12 regions of the country are expected to experience more than 100 days per year with temperatures above 30°C by 2040-2050 under a Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSP) 2-4.5 CC scenario (World Bank, 2024b). The regions most affected by heat waves are those located in the south and southeast regions, including Bukhara, Kashkadarya, Samarkand, Surxondaryo, Fergana, and Andijan.

Between 1980 and 2020, approximately 600,000 people were affected by droughts (following a major drought in 2000), and 71,550 people were affected by floods – events that occurred in 2005 and 2020 – (Figure 1). According to the Asian Development Bank (ADB) (2021), a 100-year flood could impact 6% of Uzbekistan's population (2 million people) and affect 5% (US\$ 4 billion) of the country's GDP. The eastern provinces of Fergana and Andijan, as well as the far western Republic of Karakalpakstan, are the most economically vulnerable to flooding.

Figure 1. Number of people affected by natural hazards in Uzbekistan during 1980 and 2020. Source: (World Bank, 2021).

3.2. Socioeconomic vulnerability to disasters

Uzbekistan is a middle-income country with a total population of approximately 35,648,100 people as of 2022, with an annual population growth rate of 2.1% (World Bank, 2022). The population is comprised of 50.3% female and 49.7% male. According to the World Bank (2022), 97.4% of girls and 97.8% of boys complete lower secondary school. Adult literacy rates are similar between women and men, with a slightly lower rate among females in middle-income segments. However, the labor force in the country is predominantly male, with a rate of 72.8% (World Bank, 2024a). The age structure of the population indicates that the life cycle vulnerability to disasters affects approximately 31.2% of the total population (Ibid).

Multidimensional poverty is a measure that closely reflects socioeconomic conditions that make individuals more susceptible to disasters (Fernández et al., 2023). According to UNDP (2024), 18.4% of adults (approximately 4.2 million people) are multidimensionally poor, which is the highest value in Central Asia after Tajikistan. The primary factors contributing to multidimensional poverty are education, food security, and informal employment. The regions with the highest multidimensional poverty incidence are Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya in the south, and Jizzakh and Sirdarya (Ibid). In 2023, approximately 11% of the total population lived below the national poverty line, earning less than US\$2.15 per day (ADB, 2024).

Gender-based vulnerability in Uzbekistan is evident in the disparity in living conditions between female- and male-headed households. According to The World Bank (2020), female-headed households (which represent approximately 20% of total households) are disproportionately poor and struggle more to meet basic needs and pay bills compared to male-headed households. Women's economic development faces significant barriers compared to men's, and women are disproportionately poor. A larger share of female-headed households than male-headed households borrow money for basic needs (Ibid). The gender wage gap in the country is significant, with women earning 39% less than men (Seitz & Murodova, 2022). Women are more vulnerable to income fluctuations and economic shocks and have fewer sources of income than male-headed households. In 2021, approximately 21% of female-headed households reported being unable to purchase enough food.

Given these gender disparities, an intersectional lens for CDRFI that incorporates the Differential Risk Transfer (DRT) approach (Fernández et al., 2022) is evident in Uzbekistan. The DRT approach is defined as the process of transferring financial consequences of risk from

the affected party to an insurer, considering characteristics such as gender and ethnicity, allowing access to social or financial benefits after an event.

In a climate future within the period 2020-2039, under a SSPs scenario of 4.5, the most vulnerable regions due to heat risk will be Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya, Syrdarya, and Jizzakh. Under the same scenario –which is considered the most suitable for the country (World Bank, 2024b)–, Karakalpakstan, Surkhandarya, and Jizzakh are expected to experience an increase in population until 2030, followed by stabilization during the next decade, and then a decrease starting from 2040. In contrast, Syrdarya is expected to continue experiencing a slight increase in population until 2040 and then begin to decrease from 2040 and beyond (World Bank, 2024b). As a result, there is expected to be an increase in the population of the most vulnerable regions over the next six years, which means that there will likely be an increase in socioeconomic vulnerability to heat waves and suffering from droughts if no major efforts are made in DRM.

3.3. Major recent climate-related disaster events.

In the last 25 years, more than 5 major climate-related events associated with floods and droughts have occurred in the country. However, four major events stand out in the country's recent history: the significant flood of 2000, which occurred in the first quarter of the year, and the prolonged drought period in the second quarter of 2021. The flood of 2000 was notable for its severity, with heavy rainfall and strong winds affecting the northern side of Uzbekistan, causing the overflow of the Sardoba Dam, which is located on the border with Kazakhstan. The resulting floods, which were caused by heavy rainfall and dam overflow, led to a major chain event that resulted in 50 people injured and the evacuation of 22 villages, affecting more than 70,000 people (ADRC, 2022).

In the context of CC, it is crucial to highlight the Glacial Lake Outburst Flood (GLOF) that occurred in 1998 from the Alaudyn glacier lake in the Alay range. This event resulted in over 100 fatalities from Shahimardan village.

More recently, in 2018, news agencies reported that mudflows affected 200 houses in Kashkadariyinskaya oblast, washing away 12 bridges (Takeuchi et al., 2018).

The drought of 2021 was particularly severe, lasting for one year and causing a shortage of drinking and irrigation water in the northwestern provinces. This event led to a loss of 100,000 jobs and a reduction of 50% of crop production (ADRC, 2021).

Additionally, several other notable flood-related disasters have occurred in Uzbekistan. In February 2005, a major flood and flash flood affected Kanimekh district, Navoiy province, and Nurata district, affecting 1,500 people. The most significant flood-related disaster occurred in 1998 on the Aksu and Shahimardan rivers, resulting in 109 fatalities (ADB, 2021). In April 2022, a flood in the Samarqand and Jizzakh regions killed five people and directly affected 159 people (CRED, 2024).

3.4. Disaster risk conditions

According to Takeuchi et al. (2018), floods in Uzbekistan are frequent and often have significant consequences for people's livelihoods and the economy. Floods are typically caused

by snowmelt, strong precipitation, and mountain lakes that overflow, leading to flash floods through the basin rivers.

On average, 22 flash floods and mudflows are reported annually, primarily occurring in the Chirchik and Ahangaran river valleys and in the Surkhandarya region. The high-risk areas prone to floods, flash floods, and mudflows account for approximately 12% of the country and contain over 16% of the total population. Figure 2 illustrates the country's most flood-prone areas.

Despite being located in the center of the country, regions more affected by floods are those located in the west. For example, Karakalpakstan experiences an average annual loss due to floods of US\$ 65.2 million, while Khorezm experiences an average annual loss of US\$ 55.7 million. In contrast, provinces in the east, such as Andijan and Namangan, have slightly lower average annual losses of US\$ 60.7 million and US\$ 47.2 million, respectively (CAREC, 2022).

Figure 2. Flood prone regions in Uzbekistan. Source: Adapted from UzReport, 2022. Available at: <https://uzreport.news/society/657-cases-of-floods-observed-in-uzbekistan-over-past-10-years>

Figure 3 illustrates the average annual loss by region in the country, which differs slightly from the most flood-prone regions as presented in Figure 2. The regions of Karakalpakstan, Khorezm, Bukhara, and Andijan present the highest probability of fatalities due to floods. The disparity between flood-prone areas and effectively disaster risk areas is attributed to the vulnerability of infrastructure and population. As previously mentioned, the eastern region of the country exhibits higher values of socioeconomic vulnerability and monetary poverty compared with the western regions.

According to Takeuchi et al. (2018), Glacial Lake Outburst Floods (GLOFs) are a significant risk, especially under CC scenarios that predict a faster meltdown of glaciers by 2030. Takeuchi et al. (2018) note that the country has 271 potential glacier lakes that threaten southern regions of the country. One notable example is the Usoy natural dam, located in Tajikistan, which holds

around 16 km³ of water. Its potential collapse could affect nearly 5 million people living in Tajikistan, Afghanistan, Uzbekistan, and Turkmenistan.

Figure 3. Average annual loss by floods. Source: JBA Risk Management, in CAREC (2022).

In 1998, a flood caused by a breakthrough on the Shakhimardan river, originating in the Kyrgyz Republic, killed 100 people in Uzbekistan and caused damage estimated at US\$ 700 million (Takeuchi et al., 2018). The flood caused by the Sardoba Reservoir collapse in Sirdaryo region on May 2020 resulted in the evacuation of 70,000 people who lived in the vicinity of the reservoir (UN Uzbekistan, 2020). One year later, 67,901 people – 75.9% of the 89,450 residents evacuated from Sardoba, Akaltin, and Mirzaabad districts were returned to their homes in high-risk prone areas (Kun.Uz, 2020).

According to CAREC (2022), the average annual loss caused by floods is US\$ 396.6 million, affecting approximately 220,000 people annually. Direct flood loss is modeled at around US\$ 2.8 billion at a 100-year return period, which represents circa 2.8% of the country's GDP (Ibid).

Regarding droughts, Uzbekistan can be severely affected with damages mainly in agriculture. During years of severe droughts and decreased precipitation, water supply experiences a decrease of 20-30%. CAREC (2022) notes that despite potential increases in precipitation under CC scenarios, the increase in extreme high temperatures will reduce soil and air humidity through evapotranspiration. This condition will exacerbate already dry and arid regions of the country. A worst-case scenario is depicted by UNDP (2022), which estimates that by 2050, key crop production will decrease by 25-63% compared to levels seen between 2000 and 2009.

Figure 4. Flood in Sardoba, Uzbekistan, June 2020. Source: AKIpress. Available at: https://akipress.com/news:640738:People_evacuated_by_helicopter_from_rooftops_during_flooding_in_Uzbekistan/

3.5. Disaster risk management capacities

The following sections present the DRM capacities of Uzbekistan regarding legal frameworks, risk knowledge, and financial protection. The aim of these sections is to elaborate on the state-of-the-art of the country's capacities to implement comprehensive CDRFI initiatives. By identifying current capacities, we can pinpoint gaps and needs that will inform the consolidation of a research agenda, which is the main goal of this work.

3.5.1. Institutions and legal framework for DRM and CDRFI

As the main DRM capacities of Uzbekistan to implement CDRFI and cope with climate-related events are the legal framework and institutional structure at the national level. This structure is represented by the unified system of the Ministry of Emergency Situations (MES). The MES consists of the Central Office and the Emergency Management Departments of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the regions, and the city of Tashkent, as well as the Centre of Hydrometeorological Service, the Republican Centre for Seismic Monitoring, and other subordinated organizations at the subnational level. The MES serves as the national coordinator/articulator of the DRM system and is responsible for implementing DRM through the State System of Prevention and Action in Emergency Situations –SSPAES (UNDP, 2022).

The DRM national framework recognizes the relationship between disaster and environmental degradation and advocates for a sustainable development approach. According to Article 1 of the Uzbekistan Law on the Concept of National Security (August 29, 1997), it is essential to maintain optimal ecological conditions that ensure the well-being of every individual,

safeguard public health, and establish a stable environmental situation. In this regard, there are various acts and decrees involving DRM and CDRFI, including the Law on Protection of Population and Territories from Emergency Situations of Natural and Technological Character; the Budget Code; the Annual Laws on National Budget; and the Law on Insurance Activity – including licensing insurance activities of insurance companies and insurance brokers. At the subnational levels, by-laws include a regulation on further Improvement of the Government System of Prevention of and Activities in Emergency Situations (GSCHS), and a regulation on creation of a Unified System of Monitoring, Information Exchange, and Forecasting of Emergency Situations of natural, man-made, and ecological nature.

According to Regulation #242 issued by the Cabinet of Ministers (2019), the Government of Uzbekistan has established a framework for post-disaster financing. The regulation aims to enhance the Government System of Prevention of and Activities in Emergency Situations (GSCHS), led by the MES, but involving all relevant stakeholders, including local governments, ministries, agencies, and organizations (Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2019). The regulation prioritizes the use of resources from local governments, agencies, and organizations, followed by the Cabinet of Ministers' reserve fund, and then material reserves from the Red Cross Society and international aid. Furthermore, the regulation emphasizes that local GSCHS parties should ensure adequate disaster insurance coverage for private property. Notably, a study by Takeuchi et al. (2018) found that there is a lack of guidelines, strategies, or plans to support the development of these acts, laws, and regulations. The public policy framework on DRM appears to have good intentions but lacks solid implementation, monitoring, and evaluation procedures.

According to Takeuchi et al. (2018), it remains unclear what mechanisms will be used to access external resources after the Cabinet of Ministers' reserve fund is depleted. There is no indication of established procedures for international cooperation to secure additional financial support for post-disaster recovery and reconstruction efforts. This is also connected to the same operational issues described above.

The protocols for activating the National System during and after a disaster are clear. According to the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 242 (August 24, 2011), the declaration of an emergency situation is under the responsibility of the Head of Civil Protection (Takeuchi et al., 2018). The Ministry of Emergency Situations (MES) serves as the coordinating body. Each city has an appointed person responsible for disaster risk management, namely the Mayor of the city. At the community level, community leaders are also responsible for DRM (ADRC, 2024).

Regarding preventive actions, Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 515 aims to provide civil protection from disasters through a State System of Prevention and Actions in Emergencies (President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2020b). In the case of disaster management, Cabinet of Ministers Resolution No. 747 elaborates on the procedure for compensation for disaster-related damages.

3.5.2. Disaster risk knowledge

In this section, we examine the capacities related to the risk knowledge process in DRM. A notable example is the "Central Asia Hydrometeorology Modernization Project" led by the World Bank, which has invested over US\$ 28 million to enhance the region's weather, climate, and water information services. One of its key outcomes was the provision of real-time

information sharing capabilities to the National Meteorological Service, enabling the dissemination of early warnings via SMS text messages to the general population. Additionally, weather forecasts have been made available through radio channels, benefiting economic sectors such as agriculture, energy, and tourism (World Bank, 2019b).

International literature (Takeuchi et al., 2018; World Bank, 2019b) suggests that Uzbekistan has made significant progress in incorporating risk analysis into its national DRM plan and CC adaptation plan. However, the analysis conducted during this study and the revision of the public policy framework and DRM strategies, as well as the functions of the main DRM-related institutions at the national level, drive this research to conclude that the outputs generated by risk knowledge actions are aimed at informing ex-post activities rather than informing ex-ante measures, such as risk reduction (corrective and prospective information and financial protection).

On the other hand, despite a long-standing tradition of data collection and analysis on the occurrence of climate-related events, the information is not consolidated within a single organization. Instead, various institutions are responsible for collecting and analyzing data, depending on the type of hazard. For instance, the MES handles data related to floods, while the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources (MAWR) and the State Committee on Ecology and Environment Protection are involved in flood-related data collection. Similarly, MAWR is responsible for drought-related data, and MAWR and the Ministry of Health handle extreme heat-related data. This lack of centralized information poses a significant challenge for DRM activities, including multi-risk characterization, analysis, evaluation, monitoring, and communication, as it hinders effective coordination and decision-making. Requesting this kind of data individually from every institution would add an extra burden for implementers, resulting in more expensive and ineffective DRM/CDRFI projects.

Although each institution mentioned above conducts its own analysis for sector-specific purposes, the process of collecting and normalizing data is time-consuming. This represents a significant barrier to conducting risk analysis at the local level, as it can hinder timely and efficient risk analysis, impacting decision-making and policy development. According to Takeuchi et al. (2018), p. 21), the decentralized data available raises questions about the methodology used to collect information on disaster impact and whether the impact is measured over a specific period. Similarly, it is unclear whether expenditure information is collected solely for disaster relief or reconstruction efforts. Finally, as a capacity in risk knowledge, it is worth highlighting that the committee responsible for evaluating the socio-economic and ecological consequences of a disaster, as well as the extent of damages, lacks detail in scale to create risk analysis and inform planning instruments at the local level.

3.5.3. Financial protection and climate risk insurance

In 2009, the annual average loss caused by major events in Uzbekistan was estimated at US\$ 92 million (CAREC, 2022). According to Article 71 of the Budget Code of Uzbekistan, the GoU has a specific commitment to provide financial assistance to families affected by disasters. Moreover, the state retains significant ownership of land and industry, which could result in substantial contingent liabilities for the GoU in the event of disaster recovery efforts (Takeuchi et al., 2018). A diagnostic conducted by UNDP (2022) found that Uzbekistan does not currently have any sovereign risk transfer solutions in place, nor does it have any mechanisms for transferring risk to international insurance, reinsurance, or capital markets. In this sense, the

country possesses a significant economic vulnerability to disasters, and CDRFI actions, especially those related to risk transfer, should be considered in the short term.

The Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan manages emergency funds, using the republican budget to distribute materials for reconstruction. At the local level, the Departmental Reserve provides financial and material resources for response and recovery efforts, funded by regional and local budgets and as a risk retention strategy. International organizations and foreign donors also provide support through material resources and humanitarian aid. In terms of risk transfer, according to Takeuchi et al. (2018), the country offers property disaster insurance covering fire, lightning, explosions (FLEXA insurance), earthquakes, floods, landslides, and nuclear energy impacts. However, these products do not cater to specific socioeconomic vulnerable groups, regions, or align with a national development and DRM plans.

There is a clear understanding of the role of CDRFI in reducing social inequality and vulnerability to disasters from the GoU. The GoU is committed to continuing its support to vulnerable communities by providing subsidies for essential items such as food and social protection. The country has made significant strides in adopting new approaches to improve social conditions since 2016, and this openness also extends to DRM measures. In fact, the CDRF program is seen as a way to enhance the quality of life for Uzbek citizens (Takeuchi et al., 2018). Consequently, there is a need and an opportunity to articulate social protection public policies and projects with CDRFI and CRI as a mechanism for protecting the most vulnerable to disasters.

Regarding risk insurance, the insurance industry in Uzbekistan is supervised by the State Insurance Supervision Department (Gosstrakhnadzor), under the Ministry of Finance (MoF). According to the diagnostic conducted by Takeuchi et al. (2018), in 2017, there were 27 licensed insurance companies in Uzbekistan, with four of them being life insurance companies. In 2018, the insurance penetration rate was only 0.32% of GDP, significantly lower than the global average of 6.9% and the average for emerging markets of 3.0% (ibid).

One of the main constraints on insurance expansion in Uzbekistan is that, according to AXCO (2022), despite the lack of restrictions on reinsuring abroad, Uzbekistan's reinsurance capacity is severely limited due to the depreciation of the som currency and exchange control restrictions. Furthermore, excess of loss and catastrophe reinsurance coverage is not commonly used in the country. According to CAREC (2022), there are significant opportunities to improve the CDRFI arrangements in Uzbekistan. It is estimated that around USD \$79 million is available for response to disasters. However, most of this funding is not earmarked for disaster events, and some of the funding can only be used for road reconstruction.

As mentioned previously, financial inclusion (% of population aged 15+ with access to a bank account) is low. In 2018, it was 37.1% of the total population, with a slightly lower percentage among females (36%). The insurance coverage in 2019 was 0.3%, which is below the median of Central Asia. On the other hand, approximately 10% of residential buildings in the country are insured against losses, with a significant proportion (around 84%) of these policies including earthquake coverage. However, it is expected that a substantial proportion (around 16%) of the aggregate annual loss (AAL) is not covered by existing CDRFI (CAREC, 2022).

Regarding disaster risk insurance, the UNDP (2022) notes that some local insurance companies in Uzbekistan offer products specifically designed for low-income individuals who earn USD\$ 3.70 or less per day. However, these products typically have lower coverage amounts and

premiums and have seen very little uptake. Furthermore, data analysis reveals significant gender inequality in the insurance market, with no available data on how insurance products are used and their impact, broken down by gender. Additionally, insurance penetration is limited in rural areas, with Tashkent city having a rate more than three times higher than any other region. On the supply side, the market is highly concentrated, with state-owned companies accounting for over 31% of premiums and 46% of claims, while the top five general insurers control 52% of the market (UNDP, 2022).

As specified by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2020a), the agricultural insurance market in the country is dominated by a single provider, Uzagrosugurta, a state-owned joint-stock company. Other insurance companies have exited the agricultural insurance market due to significant losses on their agricultural portfolios and increasing levels of risk affecting the sector. The government provides a subsidy for insurance premiums only to two types of crops: cotton and wheat.

4. CDRFI-related programs and projects in Uzbekistan

This section aims to provide an overview of the most relevant projects on CDRFI as part of the state of the art presented throughout this document. This section serves as input for the collection of gaps that need to be fulfilled through the research agenda.

Since 2017, the country has explored financial protection for reducing the economic burden of disasters, and CDRFI has been a priority in the last 10 years. In this context, the World Bank has actively worked with the GoU in developing programs on financial protection, with disaster risk insurance at its core. The World Bank Group's advances in Uzbekistan are part of a comprehensive CDRFI program for the Central Asia region (World Bank, 2019a).

Regarding innovative approaches, TSUE and GROSS Insurance Company from Uzbekistan have been piloting index insurance on a small scale for the last five years. These activities have been facilitated by the Insurance Lab at TSUE. The activities of the Insurance Lab have been related to ongoing projects of the Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO), such as "Increasing climate resilience via agricultural insurance in Central Asia" (KlimALEZ) and "Digital early-warning for climate crisis in Central Asia" (DETECCT) (IAMO, 2018).

Concerning public policies, to reform and ensure the accelerated development of the insurance market, the GoU launched Presidential Resolution No. PP-4412/2019 "On measures to reform and ensure the accelerated development of the insurance market of the Republic of Uzbekistan". This resolution provides guidelines and indicators to boost insurance penetration, increase the number of products, promote the development of e-insurance policies and IT solutions within a four-year timespan (2019-2022).

Despite insurance is not explicitly mentioned in the document, the National Strategy for Increasing Financial Inclusion for 2021-2023 favors future developments, as it promotes inclusive financial products such as savings, credit, payments, financial literacy, consumer protection, client-centricity, and monitoring structures to improve insurance effectiveness. The strategy has a focus on low-income and rural populations. According to UNDP (2022), the GoU is strongly motivated to implement the actions outlined in the strategy, which could create a substantial platform for CDRFI mechanisms.

Conversely, the 'Agriculture Development Strategy for 2020-2030' approved through Presidential Resolution No. PP-4575/2019 regarding "Measures for implementation of tasks defined in Strategy of Agricultural Development for period 2020-2030" includes instructions to improve credit and create new types of insurance mechanisms in agriculture.

Finally, it is relevant to mention the agricultural insurance scheme launched in September 2023 by the Insurance Development Forum (IDF), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), German Government, and GoU. This project had a total investment of EUR 1.9 million and aims to implement a risk transfer scheme consisting of a multi-hazard indemnity insurance product for spring frost, wind, hail, flood, fire, failure of irrigation, and pests/diseases to protect climate-vulnerable farmers. The project targets farmers with less than 2 hectares field size (which constitute the majority in the country) and commercial farmers located in Fergana, Namangan, and Andijan oblasts (ISF, 2023).

5. Relevant stakeholders related to Climate and Disaster Risk Finance and Insurance (CDRFI) in Uzbekistan

This chapter presents the most relevant CDRFI stakeholders, identified through the consulted literature and in previous chapters of this document. Stakeholders are categorized within the three DRM process: risk knowledge, risk reduction (which includes financial protection), and disaster management. Although the information presented is primarily intended for use within a reactive approach, it is worth noting that most of the information can be applied to both reactive and proactive approaches.

5.1. Risk knowledge-related actions:

- *State Committee on Geology and Mineral Resources* responsible for collecting data and consolidating a database on hazardous geological processes, including associated damages and losses.
- *State Committee on Architecture and Construction*: responsible for estimating disaster damages to assets and individual property, as well as estimating material resources for response and initial recovery works.
- *Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE), Insurance Lab*: a joint initiative between GROSS Insurance company and TSEU, with technical support from the Leibniz Institute of Agricultural Development in Transition Economies (IAMO). This innovation hub generates data-driven recommendations for policymakers and business partners. The Insurance Lab uses experimental methods, involving farmers and insurance representatives to develop evidence-based recommendations (IAMO, 2018).
- *United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)*: The UNDP collaborates with industry leaders and governments to develop innovative, scalable insurance, risk finance, and investment solutions (UNDP, 2024a).
- *Central Asia Regional Economic Cooperation (CAREC)*: Is a collaborative initiative that brings together 11 countries and development partners to foster economic growth and reduce poverty through regional cooperation. CAREC aims to accelerate economic development and improve the lives of people in the region (CAREC, 2024).
- *GROSS Insurance*: The insurance company "GROSS" has been operating since November 2011 under a license from the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan for all 17 classes of insurance in voluntary and compulsory forms. The company supports the development of innovative insurance products targeting the most vulnerable groups and sectors to climate-related hazards (Gross Insurance, 2024).

5.2 Risk reduction-related actions:

- *Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan*: ensures that reconstruction material and financial reserves are established and allocated for post-disaster use, guarantees that necessary financial and technical resources are available to support institutions responsible for disaster response, outlines the classification of emergency situations, defines the roles and responsibilities of executive authorities in disaster response and recovery, provides oversight of agencies involved in DRM, and monitors activities of ministries, agencies, and local executive authorities in the field of protecting the population and territories.
- *Ministry of Emergency Situations (MES)*: responsible for financing disaster response efforts from the Cabinet of Ministers' reserve fund, as well as overseeing the allocation and use of material and financial resources. The MES coordinates the establishment of various reserves, including financial, food, medical, and technical reserves, to ensure

preparedness for emergency situations. It develops and implements targeted programs and conducts research on disaster prevention and management, driving efforts to enhance the country's resilience to emergencies (DEVEX, 2024).

- *Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF)*: responsible for financing the creation of material reserves, as decided by the Cabinet of Ministers, providing financial support for response and recovery efforts after emergency situations, overseeing insurance supervision and development of financial markets, supervising the use of allocated resources, coordinating donor support and humanitarian aid, and allocating resources after disasters and proposing sources of financing for post-disaster needs (MEF, 2024).
- *Insurance Market Development Agency (IMDA)*: under the MEF, IMDA is responsible for supervising and developing the insurance market. IMDA creates a unified insurance portal to collect regular information on the state of the market, provides a centralized platform for stakeholders to access information on the insurance market, and promotes a robust and efficient insurance market that can effectively respond to the needs of individuals and businesses in the event of disasters.
- *Insurance companies*: have a critical role to play in protecting the population, particularly those living in high-risk areas. Their key responsibilities include: developing innovative insurance products that cater to the specific needs of vulnerable groups, such as low-income households, farmers, and small business owners; ensuring that these products are accessible, affordable, and tailored to the unique risks and challenges faced by these groups. Relevant companies include Gross Insurance Company, Uzagrosugurta (state-owned insurer), and Kafolat (state-owned insurer).

5.3 Disaster management-related actions:

- *Local governments*: are the first line of defense against disasters. Their key responsibilities include: creating financial reserves to respond to disasters, financing the liquidation of emergency situations, designing and implementing contingency plans and strategies for disaster recovery and reconstruction (CAREC, 2022).
- *Ministry of Health*: is responsible for supplying essential medicines to affected areas, providing first aid to the affected population, controlling and preventing epidemics in the aftermath of a disaster, and ensuring the overall health and well-being of those affected by disasters (Ministry of Health, 2024).
- *Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources*: is responsible for providing critical support to farmers during disaster response efforts. Their key responsibilities include conducting sanitary-and-veterinary control in affected areas to prevent the spread of disease, implementing epizootic control measures to protect animal health, monitoring dams, and preparing for potential floods in collaboration with the Ministry of Emergency Situations (MAWR, 2024).

6. Most relevant sectors for implementing CDRFI mechanisms in Uzbekistan

This section presents the most relevant sectors for implementing CDRF. The relevance is related to the sector's vulnerability to climate-related hazards and the economic significance of the sector to the national GDP and population's wellbeing.

6.1 Public sector

The most needed institutions for incorporating an approach on CDRFI are DRM-related institutions, particularly the technical agencies responsible for producing data and information about the characteristics of hazards, details on socioeconomic, institutional, and physical vulnerability, and for conducting risk assessments and communicating risk conditions. According to Takeuchi et al. (2018), the collection of information must focus on disaster risks, impacts, and post-disaster expenditure by region and city. Although the country collects disaster loss data, the information is not formalized, and its management is spread across different agencies. Moreover, risk modeling and scenarios show an insufficient assessment of hazard's financial consequences, which limits the prioritization of infrastructure, goods, and regions within a financial protection strategy. Finally, considering the high number of public assets and state-owned companies, the public sector should consider highly relevant the implementation of a multi-layer DRF strategy that includes national and subnational DRM funds, contingent credit arrangements, catastrophe bonds, and sovereign insurance. These financial instruments should be articulated with other development planning instruments, such as the Uzbekistan Development Strategy 2022-2026 and the National Action Plan to Increase Resilience to Disasters and Climate Change 2023-2030 (Government of Uzbekistan, 2023). The relevant institutions to achieve this are the MES and the Ministry of Finance, as coordinators of the CDRFI component of the DRM-related system.

6.2 Private sector

The agricultural sector represents more than 28% of the country's GDP, with significant expansion, approximately 2.8% over the past seven years (UNDP, 2022). This sector requires subnational risk modeling for assessing the most vulnerable areas and expected losses from spring frost, strong winds, floods, and droughts. Developing regional financial protection strategies is necessary, with the agricultural sector at its core. The MAWR should develop specific contingency plans, in coordination with the MES and the Ministry of Finance, to ensure differentiated responses by region and by type of hazard. The target population should be the most vulnerable to climate-related hazards, such as small-scale farmers with less than 2 hectares of field and low-income commercial farmers specializing in fruit and vegetable production.

To implement capacity building, strengthen sector cohesion and articulation, the MAWR should work with regional authorities to promote the consolidation of producer associations. Through these associations, a macro- and meso-level insurance scheme can be established, promoting long-term sustainability. A better understanding of the demand side from insurance companies is needed to benefit the agricultural sector, particularly small farmers. This understanding requires generating sex-disaggregated data, monitoring and evaluating insurance payouts with a gender- and ethnicity-responsive lens, and constant communication with local and national DRM-related authorities on data needs or availability to improve the impacts of CDRFI at the micro level.

7. Identification of topics for a potential CDRFI research agenda

This chapter presents the research topics that are crucial for developing CDRFI in Uzbekistan. The topics are presented by type of component in the developing process for DRM and CC adaptation. These have been classified into six categories: (i) data, (ii) risk knowledge, (iii) capacity building, (iv) innovative solutions, (v) legal framework, and (vi) demand side research. These topics have been identified considering the disaster risk conditions in Uzbekistan, CDRFI-related programs and projects, relevant stakeholders involved, and the identification of the most relevant sectors for implementing CDRFI, as presented in previous chapters (Figure 5). Table 1 presents the timetable with a coherent timespan in which the most significant activities can be implemented simultaneously or considering inputs from other activities. Times in Table 1 are merely a reference for its implementation.

Figure 5. Inputs and outputs for the definition of topics for a CDRFI research agenda in Uzbekistan.

The topics are intended to be researched by relevant stakeholders, as presented in Chapter 4, within a multi-stakeholder approach and within the framework of Uzbekistan's DRM system, encompassing both national and subnational levels. Most of the topics focus on strengthening prevention rather than reactive practices. In all cases, the Technical University of Engineering (TSUE) as a research and academic institution plays a vital role in leading cross-cutting actions and articulating public and private sector efforts.

Data: The research should be focused on collecting, analyzing and communicating data on:

- Developing a centralized system, managed by the MES, for collecting, sharing, and analyzing data on disaster damages (infrastructure destroyed and livelihoods affected) and losses (cost of business interruption, long-term impact on community development).
- Collecting sex-disaggregated data on the impacts of hazards and socioeconomic vulnerability.
- Collecting sex-disaggregated data on the perception and willingness to use CRI.
- Collecting sex-disaggregated data on insurance coverage.
- Analyzing the impacts of climate-related hazards on ethnic groups and scenarios in a future climate.

Risk knowledge products:

- Development of probabilistic modeling of damage and losses for financial planning and planning instruments such as DRM and CC adaptation plans, as well as regional and local development plans.
- Analysis of post-disaster expenditure by type of phase, including response, recovery, and reconstruction.
- Quantification of Uzbekistan's fiscal risk due to disasters, considering different CC scenarios.
- Development of a multi-layered approach to risk financing, considering fiscal allocations, reinsurance, capital markets, donors, and other risk financing options.
- Incorporation of risk knowledge products into the DRF national strategy.

Capacity building:

- Strengthen the capacity of local insurers to design and deliver client-centric products.
- Development of strategic guidelines to implement CDRFI mechanisms for public assets.
- Development of strategic guidelines to integrate risk transfer into development plans at the national and subnational levels.
- Development of strategic guidelines among insurers and the Insurer Association on the design of effective and clear claims payment, aiming to improve customer's insurance trust.
- Development of strategic guidelines from the Insurance Market Development Agency (IMDA) and the MES for the design and implementation of solutions for low-income and rural Uzbeks with effective and efficient delivery methods (UNDP, 2022).
- Development of an insurance training center in partnership with the TSUE to design and deliver capacity-building programs for insurers, public servants, including staff from the IMDA and MES.
- Development of case studies on how to link the local reinsurance sector to international partnerships.
- Development of best practices guidelines on how to advance the reinsurance sector.
- Exploration of partnerships with international insurtech, insurance, and reinsurance companies to exchange good practices and public-private partnerships.
- Exploration of partnerships and increased interaction with insurance supervisors, such as the Access to Insurance Initiative (A2ii), to support relevant insurance, banking, telecommunications, and other regulatory local agencies.

Innovative solutions:

- Research on digitalization and innovation for access to financial services and financial literacy, particularly for rural communities and agricultural producers' associations, as well as women.

- Development of a CRI communication and awareness strategy for the national, regional, and local levels.
- Development of microinsurance products specifically targeting the most vulnerable populations to floods in the middle and western regions of the country.
- Development of a communication campaign to promote a positive perception of customers about insurance companies.
- Research on international multi-donor funds and initiatives to increase subsidies on premiums for risk transfer products for poor and vulnerable customers, especially women and women-headed households.
- Exploration of public-private smart subsidy schemes within the blended finance model to increase private sector participation in sectoral DRM.
- Development of blended finance projects to encourage public sector investment in market development and socially-inclusive insurance premiums and risk transfer strategies for low-income municipalities.
- Research on alternative models for CRI subsidies for agriculture and risk transfer mechanisms for response and recovery.
- Support for the introduction of index-based insurance products, considering the current capacities of the TSEU's Insurance Lab and its pilot programs.
- Research on the articulation of risk transfer to social protection public policies and projects envisioned for the short and long-term.

Legal framework and public policies:

- Development of guidelines to support regulations at the national and subnational levels.
- Development of consultative workshops to establish the legal structure and definition of inclusive insurance, and its incorporation in planning instruments and strategies.
- Definition of standards to implement CRI in the most vulnerable regions.
- Development of a legal framework for compulsory insurance for the agricultural sector.
- Analysis of the regulatory framework considering the core principles of the International Association of Insurance Supervisors (IAIS).
- Development of best practices to integrate insurance within the structure and activities of the National Strategy for Increasing Financial Inclusion 2021-2023 as a cross-cutting activity.

Demand side:

- Research on the roots of limited consumer trust in insurance companies.
- Characterization of the low-income market, their risks, and perceptions about disasters.
- Development of public-private partnerships to increase demand-side information.
- Research on how to improve the protection of producers' property interests.
- Development of a methodological framework to enhance financial sustainability for agricultural producers and insurers.

8. Time table for the implementation of the research agenda

HUB (H)	ACTIVITY	Year 1												Year 2								
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
H1	Data																					
	Developing a centralized system for collecting/analyzing disaster loss data																					
	Collecting sex-disaggregated data on the willingness to use CRI.																					
	Collecting sex-disaggregated data on insurance coverage.																					
H2	Risk knowledge products																					
	Probabilistic modeling of damage and losses for financial planning																					
	Analysis of post-disaster expenditure																					
	Quantification of Uzbekistan's fiscal risk																					
H3	Guidelines for incorporation risk knowledge into the DRF national strategy																					
	Capacity building																					
	Strengthen the capacity of local insurers and public institutions																					
H4	Development of an insurance training center																					
	Partnerships and increased interaction with insurance supervisors																					
	Innovative solutions:																					
H5	Digitalization and innovation for access to financial services and literacy																					
	International multi-donor funds and initiatives to increase subsidies																					
	Articulation of risk transfer to social protection public policies																					
H5	Legal framework and public policies																					
	Guidelines to support regulations at the national and subnational levels																					
H6	Definition of standards to implement CRI in the most vulnerable regions																					
	Demand side																					
H6	Research on the roots of limited consumer trust in insurance companies																					
	Public-private partnerships to increase demand-side information																					

9. Conclusions

Climate-related hazards are the most prevalent in Uzbekistan. These types of hazards affect the agricultural sector, primarily through seasonal flooding and droughts. The country has the second-highest multidimensional poverty index value in Central Asia, with gender-based vulnerability evident in the disparity in living conditions between female- and male-headed households. Direct flood loss is estimated at approximately US\$ 2.8 billion at a 100-year return period, which represents around 2.8% of the country's GDP.

The country offers property disaster insurance covering fire, lightning, explosions, earthquakes, floods, landslides, and nuclear energy impacts. However, these products do not cater to specific socioeconomic vulnerable groups, regions, or align with national development and DRM plans.

The identification of past and current programs and projects related to CDRFI in the country provided a state-of-the-art overview of experiences and gaps regarding CRI, risk transfer, and risk retention. Similarly, the review of gray and academic literature allowed for the identification of stakeholders involved in the development of DRM and CDRFI; this constitutes the basis for a future stakeholder mapping exercise.

Notable DRM frameworks and programs that enable the expansion of CDRFI in the country include Presidential Resolution No. PP-4412/2019 "On measures to reform and ensure the accelerated development of the insurance market." The National Strategy for Increasing Financial Inclusion for 2021–2023 and the Agriculture Development Strategy for 2020–2030.

The research agenda's components, grouped into data, risk knowledge, capacity building, innovative solutions, legal framework, and demand-side research, focus mainly on prevention, aiming to transition from the current government's reactive approach to a more comprehensive approach that integrates knowledge, risk reduction, and sustainable development.

The research topics form a compact set of possible actions that can be incorporated into national and regional DRM plans and as part of the DRF strategy. These research topics are not the responsibility of a single institution or company but are part of a multisectoral development strategy that should be coordinated by the MES.

The identified research topics directly emerged from the sections (chapters) and subsections of this document. Each section made a specific contribution to identifying gaps and weaknesses in CDRFI in Uzbekistan. The summary of the research agenda's translation into a timetable for future implementation allows different stakeholders to consider activities in a systematic order according to priorities.

Due to the limited timeframe of this study, this research relied solely on gray and academic literature to elaborate on the research topics, excluding primary data such as interviews with key national and international stakeholders. Future studies should include (sub)national actors for validation and deliberation of their perspectives on CDRFI, particularly regarding social vulnerability and risk transfer for private and public assets.

Acknowledgements

This work was conducted within the framework of the CARSI project (No. 101086415) Caucasus and Central Asia Research Social Innovation: Development Assistance, Innovation, and Societal Transformation, funded by the Horizon Marie Curie Staff Exchange programme, Faculty of Economics, University of Coimbra. The mobility was based at the Tashkent State University of Economics (TSUE) in Tashkent, Uzbekistan. The author would like to extend his gratitude to the Department of Digital Economy, particularly to Dr. Azizjon Bobonojov, Dr. Raya Karlibaeva, and Dr. Abdumalik Abdurakhmonov for their professional support and hospitality during the mobility period. Special thanks to Dr. Maria Raquel Freire from the Faculty of Economics of the University of Coimbra and Dr. Abel Polese from Dublin City University for promoting knowledge and cultural exchange between Europe and Central Asia.

10. References

- ADB. (2021). Uzbekistan climate risk country profile. Retrieved May 27, 2024, www.worldbank.org
- ADB. (2024). Poverty in Uzbekistan. Retrieved May 23, 2024, <https://www.adb.org/where-we-work/uzbekistan/poverty>
- ADRC. (2021). Uzbekistan's drought of 2001. Retrieved May 22, 2024, https://www.adrc.asia/view_disaster_en.php?NationCode=860&Lang=en&Key=189
- ADRC. (2022). Uzbekistan's floods of 2020. Retrieved May 22, 2024, from Asian Disaster Reduction Center: https://www.adrc.asia/view_disaster_en.php?NationCode=860&Lang=en&Key=2382
- ADRC. (2024). Uzbekistan: Information on disaster risk reduction of the member countries. Retrieved May 22, 2024, <https://www.adrc.asia/nationinformation.php?NationCode=860&Lang=en&NationNum=04>
- Alimonti, G., and Mariani, L. (2023). Is the number of global natural disasters increasing? *Environmental Hazards*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17477891.2023.2239807>
- Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekista. Approval of regulations of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, (2019).
- CAREC. (2022). Country risk profile Uzbekistan. Retrieved June 03, 2024, https://www.carecprogram.org/uploads/CAREC-Risk-Profiles_Uzbekistan.pdf
- CAREC. (2024). CAREC Program. Retrieved June 26, 2024, https://www.carecprogram.org/?page_id=31
- CRED. (2023). Disasters in numbers 2022. Retrieved June 26, 2024, https://www.cred.be/sites/default/files/2022_EMDAT_report.pdf
- CRED. (2024). Public EM-DAT platform, Uzbekistan. Retrieved May 22, 2024, <https://public.emdat.be/>
- Delavallade, C., Dizon, F., Hill, R. V., & Petraud, J. P. (2015). Managing risk with insurance and Savings: experimental evidence for male and female farm managers in West Africa.

- In IFPRI (No. 01426). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2583847>
- DEVEX. (2024). About the Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved June 26, 2024, <https://www.devex.com/organizations/ministry-of-emergency-situations-uzbekistan-mes-207008>
- DRFIP. (2023). Financial protection of public assets through public asset registry and risk transfer. Retrieved June 12, 2024, https://www.financialprotectionforum.org/publication/disaster-risk-finance-instruments-financial-protection-of-public-assets-through-public?mc_cid=4892d23532&mc_eid=8beaaa4a76
- Fernández Lopera, C. C. (2020). La protección financiera para la gestión del riesgo de desastres en América Latina. *Revista de Estudios Latinoamericanos Sobre Reducción Del Riesgo de Desastres REDER*, 4(2), 22–35. <https://doi.org/10.55467/reder.v4i2.48>
- Fernández Lopera, C. C., Mendes, J. M., and Barata, E. J. (2022). The Differential risk transfer: a new approach for reducing vulnerability to climate-related hazards. *Disaster Prevention and Management: An International Journal*, 31(5), 550–564. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DPM-05-2021-0185>
- Fernández Lopera, C. C., Mendes, J. M., Barata, E. J., and Sandoval, V. (2023). Prioritization of territorial areas for implementing inclusive climate risk transfer mechanisms. Colombia as a Case Study. *IDRiM Journal*, 13(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.5595/001c.77526>
- Government of Uzbekistan. National action plan for improving resilience to natural disasters and climate change. (2023).
- Gross Insurance. (2024). About Gross Insurance Company. Retrieved June 26, 2024, <https://gross.uz/ru/about-us>
- IAMO. (2018). Establishment of insurance laboratory in Uzbekistan. Retrieved June 25, 2024, <https://www.iamo.de/en/news/news/article/establishment-of-insurance-laboratory-in-uzbekistan/>
- ISF. (2023). Insurance product in Uzbekistan. Retrieved June 17, 2024, www.insuresilience-solutions-fund.org
- Kun.Uz. (2020). About 76 percent of those evacuated in Syrdarya returned to their homes. Retrieved May 28, 2024, <https://kun.uz/en/news/2020/06/03/about-76-percent-of-those-evacuated-in-syrdarya-returned-to-their-homes>
- Marulanda, M. C., Cardona, O. D., Mora, M. G., and Barbat, A. H. (2014). Design and implementation of a voluntary collective earthquake insurance policy to cover low-income homeowners in a developing country. *Natural Hazards*, 74(3), 2071–2088. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-014-1291-4>
- MAWR. (2024). Task of the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved June 27, 2024, https://gov.uz/en/activity_page/agriculture/
- MEF. (2024). About the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved June 26, 2024, <https://www.imv.uz/en/static/biz-haqimizda>
- Ministry of Health. (2024). Tasks and functions of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Retrieved June 27, 2024, <https://gov.uz/en/ssv/pages/vazirlik-vazifalari-va-funksiyalari/>
- President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On measures to implement in 2020 the tasks defined in the Agricultural Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2030.

- (2020).
- President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On measures to radically improve the system for ensuring seismic safety of the population and territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2020).
- PreventionWeb. (2023). Uzbekistan: PPP launched to develop agriculture insurance scheme. Retrieved June 25, 2024, <https://www.preventionweb.net/news/public-private-partnership-launched-develop-agriculture-insurance-scheme-uzbekistan>
- Seitz, W., and Murodova, S. (2022). Examining the scale of gender discrimination in hiring practices in Uzbekistan. Retrieved May 21, 2024, <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/europeandcentralasia/examining-scale-gender-discrimination-hiring-practices-uzbekistan>
- Takeuchi, K., Skalon, T., and Gurenko, E. (2018). Disaster risk finance country note: Uzbekistan. Retrieved May 29, 2024, <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/en/513951591597853635/pdf/Disaster-Risk-Finance-Country-Note-Uzbekistan.pdf>
- Tang, Y., Cai, H., and Liu, R. (2021). Farmers' demand for informal risk management strategy and weather index insurance: evidence from China. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13753-021-00335-9>
- UN Uzbekistan. (2020). Citizens affected from flooding in Syrdarya region will receive financial assistance. Retrieved May 28, 2024, <https://www.un.int/uzbekistan/fr/news/citizens-affected-flooding-syrdarya-region-will-receive-financial-assistance>
- UNDP. (2022). Inclusive insurance and risk financing in Uzbekistan: Snapshot and way forward 2022. Retrieved June 11, 2024, <https://irff.undp.org/sites/default/files/2022-12/summary-country-diagnostic-uzbekistan.pdf>
- UNDP. (2024a). Insurance & Risk Finance Facility. Retrieved June 26, 2024, <https://irff.undp.org/>
- UNDP. (2024b). Uzbekistan multidimensional poverty index report 2023. Retrieved May 23, 2024, United Nations Development Programme: <https://www.undp.org/uzbekistan/publications/uzbekistan-pilot-multidimensional-poverty-index-report-2023>
- UNDRR. (2005). Hyogo Framework for Action 2005-2015. Retrieved from <https://www.eird.org/cdmah/contenido/hyogo-framework-spanish.pdf>
- UNGA. (2015). Sendai framework for disaster risk reduction 2015-2030. Geneva.
- World Bank. (2019a). Central Asia, building resilience against disasters. Retrieved May 22, 2024, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/video/2019/05/03/central-asia-building-resilience-against-natural-disasters>
- World Bank. (2019b). Improving weather, climate, and hydrological services in Central Asia. Retrieved May 21, 2024, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/video/2018/12/19/improving-weather-climate-and-hydrological-services-in-central-asia>
- World Bank. (2020). As winter approaches, female-headed households in Uzbekistan often struggle to pay for utilities and basic needs. Retrieved May 21, 2024, <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/infographic/2020/12/23/energy-vulnerability-of->

[female-headed-households-in-uzbekistan](#)

World Bank. (2021). Uzbekistan, historical hazards. Retrieved May 22, 2024, <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/uzbekistan/vulnerability>

World Bank. (2022). Uzbekistan: sociodemographic data. Retrieved May 23, 2024, <https://data.worldbank.org/country/uzbekistan>

World Bank. (2024a). Uzbekistan: World Bank gender data portal. Retrieved May 23, 2024, from World Bank gender data portal website: <https://genderdata.worldbank.org/en/economies/uzbekistan>

World Bank. (2024b). Uzbekistan heat risk. Retrieved May 22, 2024, from Climate Change Knowledge Portal website: <https://climateknowledgeportal.worldbank.org/country/uzbekistan/heat-risk>